

ECOBULK

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Report on material conditioning processes

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, titled “Report on material conditioning processes” aims to find the best process to enhance recovered material stream. The deliverable will be based on the material (samples, solvents, equipment for separation) and methods (chemical separation with DMSO) for fibres and plastic cleaning; and the materials (samples, DBD plasma equipment and microbiological material) and methods (DoE of DBD plasma treatment, contact angle measurement and microbiological methods) for the surface activation for reuse.

Cleaning pre-treatment of EoL materials by chemical separation with DMSO have been validated for fibers and plastics. Polyester fibers and wind turbine blades treatment processes have shown the best results in terms of material cleaning from contaminants like polyurethanes. Both processes provide materials that can be re-introduced in the closed loop developed in the project. Automotive scraps treatment showed good results only for the partial removal of PC from ABS/PC components. Further process investigation should be discussed with key project partners to explore industrial implementation of the technology.

Plasma treatment have been successfully applied for surface modification of furniture, automotive and building materials in the present deliverable for reuse. For wooden materials, plasma surface activation technology is an effective path to modify the surface of the material, as long as the surface is non-porous and the plasma treated wooden material would ideally be reused after 2 days. On the other hand, for automotive and building materials treated by cold plasma, a recommendation to reuse the materials right after the treatment is suggested.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

<i>ABS</i>	<i>Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene</i>
<i>ASR</i>	<i>Automotive scraps residues</i>
<i>CFU</i>	<i>colony-forming unit</i>
<i>DBD</i>	<i>Dielectric barrier discharge</i>
<i>DMAC</i>	<i>N,N-Dimetilacetamida</i>
<i>DMF</i>	<i>Dimethylformamide</i>
<i>DMSO</i>	<i>Dimethylsulfoxide</i>
<i>DSC</i>	<i>Differential scanning calorimetry</i>
<i>ELV</i>	<i>End-of-life vehicles</i>
<i>IR</i>	<i>Infra-red</i>
<i>NMP</i>	<i>N-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidone</i>
<i>PAN</i>	<i>Polyacrylonitrile</i>
<i>PC</i>	<i>Polycarbonate</i>
<i>PCA</i>	<i>Plate count agar</i>
<i>PES</i>	<i>Polyethersulfone</i>
<i>PLA</i>	<i>Polylactic acid</i>
<i>PP</i>	<i>Polypropylene</i>
<i>PS</i>	<i>Polyester</i>
<i>PU</i>	<i>Polyurethane</i>
<i>RNS</i>	<i>Reactive nitrogen species</i>
<i>ROS</i>	<i>Reactive oxygen species</i>
<i>TSB</i>	<i>Tryptone soy agar</i>
<i>UV</i>	<i>Ultraviolet</i>
<i>WCA</i>	<i>Water contact angle</i>
<i>WTB</i>	<i>Wind turbine blades</i>

1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the document and pursue

This document aims to analyse the state of the art of the different conditions of DBD plasma treatment on material conditioning. In this context, IRIS Science Department has been involved on the development/conditioning materials for circular designed products, evaluating the effectiveness of DBD-plasma for microbial inactivation as well as the surface activation of ECOBULK-project materials.

The intended audience of this document includes the development teams, exploitation stakeholders and operations teams of the ECOBULK project.

This deliverable will be used by the ECOBULK partners as the specification document to know how to optimize the parameters of DMSO cleaning process and DBD plasma for the application on reuse materials.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

This document intends to cover part of the purpose of the task 3.4 which deals with “Material conditioning and preparation for new material supply chains”.

Furthermore, Subtask 3.4.1 studies “Fibres and plastics cleaning by DMSO”. Also, Subtask 3.4.2 evaluates the “Surface activation for reuse” of the different sectors: textiles, automotive, furniture and building.

Moreover, the content of this document is closely related with work package 5 and more specifically with task 5.3 named “Current Bulky and ELV waste streams: revalorization for integration in circular material supply chain”.

The tasks previously listed are contained in the work package 3 named “Material development/conditioning for circular designed products” and this deliverable explains the. The specific objectives of the present document are as follows:

- ✓ To validate DMSO treatment process for fibres and plastics cleaning avoiding the use of toxic chemicals for contaminants removal. Bath ratio, treatment time and temperature will be optimized by considering the technical and financial viability of the technology.
- ✓ The use and recovery of DMSO could reduce the cost in treatment of recovered materials and reduce the impact on the environment produced by conventional

technologies (organic solvents or washes) together with a decrease in the consumption of water/solvent.

- ✓ To validate the best conditions to produce effective plasma with different materials (samples) provided by the partners will be studied. Parameters such as air gap, treatment time (in continuous or in batch), atmospheric air and other parameters will be tested.
- ✓ To assess the superficial microbicide effect of DBD-plasma in bacterial and subrogates of pathogen microorganism (Gram (+/-) bacteria, i.e. Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus Aureus.) will be evaluated. After the treatment, each microorganism decontamination will be evaluated by direct count in the appropriate culture medium.
- ✓ To activate the surface of the reused materials. Hence, the data generated by the assessments carried out on the plasma treated samples will be directly related to the strength of the adhesion between the particle and the matrix as well as being used as interlayer at the multilayer panels assembled.

2. Methods: Material conditioning pre-treatments

Conditioning of materials could be carried out by different technologies. The use of non-thermal emerging technologies on decontamination of surfaces, packaging and food products and on surfaces and materials activation is an increasing focus of interest since there are no damages by heat on products, materials or containers. Among different non-thermal technologies, cold plasma has recently drawn considerable interest due to its effectiveness in reducing microbial contamination as well as the surface activation (change in material properties to enhance its permeability or its adhesion properties) effect.

Also, DMSO cleaning, which is a nontoxic pre-treatment and non-polluting compound, can avoid the use of toxic chemicals and the leakage of water or solvents as a solvent recycling process.

In this deliverable, initial pre-treatments were required for some raw materials and the current recycled streams (plastics and fibers from ELV and MBW plus wood) to meet the specifications defined for the material and product development (Task 2.3). These pre-treatments technologies are already validated in relevant environment (TRL5) and will be adjusted according to the raw material properties and their contamination level.

2.1. Chemical separation with Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO)

The selective extraction is a commonly known chemical purification process and the employment for plastic recycling is based on the knowledge that different solvents like tetrahydrofuran (THF), xylene, methylethylketone (MEK) or dichloromethane (DCM) can selectively dissolve fossil-based polymers (*Achillas et al 2009*). The process is applied for many different polymers (polypropylene, polyamides, polyolefin) and reveals adequate dissolution kinetics and polymer qualities (*Papaspyrides and Kartalis 2000*); however, the recycling of metal-plastic composites and larger scale trials are not reported. Other typical candidates are cyclohexane, cyclohexanone, acetone and limonene. Because the typical solvents for the selective extraction carry a high hazard potential, the development of new processes specialized in the application of solvents with the lowest possible risk potential for the users and the environment, are still under development in order to enable a safe circular economy. The CreaSolv[®] Process (CreaSolv[®] is a registered trademark of CreaCycle GmbH), developed and patented by the Fraunhofer Institute for Process Engineering and Packaging IVV, uses special formulations with a low risk for both users and the environment. After the cleaning from impurities the desired polymer precipitates when a special CreaSolv[®] Precipitation agent is added. These selective solvents-mixtures extract the target polymers from heterogeneous waste input streams, allowing the polymer solution to be separated from undissolved components or harmful and/or prohibited pollutants, such as plasticizers or halogenic flame retardants. At the end of the process, the solvent is recovered by drying in order to ensure closed-loop circulation and to keep the process economically viable. The recycled polymer (product) is solvent free, meets the properties of virgin material, and is suitable as a substitute material in production processes. By using DMSO solvent, ECOBULK aims to achieve the same cleaning results based on plastic dissolution and following gelification without using toxic chemicals as precipitation agents and avoiding the waste production. The recovered solvent could be distilled for further re-use while the remaining insoluble impurities are collected to be waste-handle. DMSO has low acute and chronic toxicity for animal, plant and aquatic life. DMSO is not listed as a carcinogen by regulatory authorities and is actually used as a neutral solvent in the Ames mutagenicity tests.

DMSO Industrial Grade is a technical grade of Dimethyl Sulfoxide, suitable for use in common industrial formulations (such as solvent cleaning applications and paint stripping). This nontoxic polar solvent plays an important role in the synthesis and processing of polymers, including polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and polyethersulfone (PES). DMSO is an effective solvent for removing organic materials from equipment lines and manufacturing equipment. DMSO exhibits high solubility for many polymers and may aid in polymer processing and clean-up. An important example is the use of DMSO as a

nontoxic alternative to more hazardous solvents in paint stripping formulations. DMSO Industrial Grade is used as a reaction solvent in manufacturing a variety of polymers. Additional downstream applications include as a processing solvent in operations such as casting polymeric membranes and wet-spinning synthetic fibers.

In Subtask 3.4.1, the main streams coming from the physical and mechanical separation process (wind turbine blades by CONENOR, car scraps by Tomra and Light fraction from vehicles shredding by Bellver) have been tested by the solvolysis process available at NTT. Mixture of different polymeric materials can be easily separated by dissolving each component in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO – it has been selected since it has low acute and chronic toxicity for animal, plant and aquatic life, thus it is safer than conventional solvents used in polymer separation) heating the solution at different temperature in the range 100-200°C and different bath ratio (1:2 - 1:5) and treatment time have been optimized by considering both technical and financial viability. The range has been selected according to preliminary tests carried out at NTT with mixtures of polymers coming from textile industry and thermoset composites. Each polymer is selectively separated from the mixture, according to their different softening and melting temperature and recovered by precipitation at high purity (contamination < 2-4%). Due to the complexity of solvent-based recycling plants, the investment costs for the required equipment are fairly high in comparison to those for conventional mechanical recycling.

2.2. DBD Plasma generation system

On one hand, the antimicrobial mechanism of action of plasma is based on triggering a complex sequence of biological responses in microorganism's inactivation by different agents. Those agents are ultraviolet irradiation, charge particles and reactive species, formed by the presence of air (Moreau *et al.*, 2008; Fridman *et al.*, 2007; Misra *et al.*, 2011). The most important reactive species involved onto this action are Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) and Reactive Nitrogen Species (RNS). In addition, time and initial microbial population are factors to be considered onto the plasma antimicrobial effectivity (Ziuzina *et al.*, 2013). Some studies demonstrate DBD plasma effectivity against bacterial pathogens such as *Escherichia Coli* or *Listeria Monocytogenes* (Misra *et al.*, 2011), most of them are focused on food's surface decontamination (Leipold *et al.*, 2011).

On the other hand, the material activation could be generated by different origins. One of them is the energy generated during plasma treatment. This energy can crack chemical bonds in materials (polymer of plastics or other surfaces). The open bonds can react with chemical substances (for example glues) or functional groups can be attached to them in the plasma. Other possibility is the electromagnetic radiation created in the plasma. This radiation is strong enough to crack bonds in the polymer. Some atoms are

excited in the plasma. They emit radiation in the range of infrared to ultraviolet (UV). The UV radiation is the part that has enough energy to crack bonds. In this sense, plasma material activation is a technology that can be used to increase the wettability of the surfaces for the adhesion of binding components for painting, gluing, printing or bonding. Not only is wetting prevented by oil and grease marks, but also the clean surface of many materials cannot be sufficiently wetted by many liquids, adhesives and inks. The applied liquid would roll off and would not adhere to the surface after curing or drying. The cause is a low surface energy of the substrate. Substances having a low surface energy wet those with a high surface energy, but not vice versa. The surface energy of the applied liquid, also referred to as surface tension, must be lower than that of the substrate in each case (<https://www.plasma.com/en/applications/plasma-activation/>). The surface activation has been tested in different plastics with high success and its activation remains effective over weeks and months and it can be also applied on metal surfaces, wood or glass materials.

Until relative recently, plasma could only be generated under vacuum and high temperature, but the new advances on technology achieve its formation under atmosphere conditions. Thus, DBD atmospheric plasma is the most convenient way for plasma generation, with respect to electrode configuration, its flexibility and the possibility to scale-up to industrial applications (Fridman *et al.*, 2007). In addition, there are some studies that use other atmosphere gasses such as argon.

2.3. Assessment of hydrophobicity of surfaces

To test the plasma effectivity on modifying the treated surfaces, measurements of their water contact angle (WCA) were performed according to the sessile drop technique. The static contact angle of all samples was analyzed immediately after applying the plasma treatment, thus distilled water was used as test liquid. A water drop was uniformly placed on the surface and the image was recorded by a camera device of Advex Instruments (Belgium). After that, images were analyzed to determine the contact angle by See System software (version 6.2.). When the contact angle is 0° , the liquid spreads over the solid surface. In contrast, if θ is 180° , the liquid does not wet the solid surface. A solid surface is considered wettable if the contact angle is less than 90° ; whereas the surface is not wettable when θ is above 90° (López-García, 2019). All values reported are the mean of 5 data points done in triplicates, plus their corresponding standard error. In addition, with the results of water contact angle, it was possible to estimate the wettability modification rate (%) of each treated sample.

2.4. Effect on antimicrobial activity

“Cold plasma” has become one of the novel non-thermal decontamination technologies for medical devices, air flows and tissues, food-packaging and textile industries while it’s currently opening up to many other industrial applications (Brandenburg & Brandenburg, 2017; Ibis, Oflaz, & Ercan, 2016; Pankaj et al., 2017; Virk, Ramaswamy, Bourham, & Bures, 2004) .

The microbiological count of furniture samples was evaluated before and after plasma treatment. The rest of the samples presented lower porosity, so they were inoculated at IRIS’ laboratory before evaluating the antibacterial activity of the plasma treatment. The strains used for this purpose were one of each Gram positive and negative bacteria, respectively, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. These organisms were selected on the basis of being indicators of the presence of the most typical families of microorganisms of the skin flora: Staphylococci and Enterobacteriaceae (Höfer, 2006; Archana, Dutta and Dutta, 2013; Li et al., 2016).

The antimicrobial efficacy of the DBD plasma treatment was evaluated by a rinsing and plate counting method (Balestra and Misaghi, 1997; Ismail et al., 2013). Consistently, fiber glass samples were weight until 100 mg and a section of 4x4 cm for all the other samples (furniture, automotive and building) was taken into account for the analyses. All samples were sterilized under UV light for 30 min and each piece was kept in sterile conditions. After that, two sets of duplicated samples were inoculated with 100 µl of *S. aureus* subcultured in tryptone soy broth (TSB) at 37 °C for 24 h, containing 1x10⁷ -1x10⁹ CFU/ml. In parallel, another couple of set of duplicates was inoculated with 100 µl of *E. coli* subcultured in TSB at 37 °C for 24 h, containing 1x10⁷ -1x10⁹ CFU/ml. Samples were dried under sterile air stream flow before applying the plasma treatment. One set of each inoculated duplicate remained untreated as the control reference.

Immediately after plasma treatment, every sample was placed in a sterile flask containing 20 ml of Ringer ¼ (homogenate) and shaken for 1 min with a vortex at maximum speed. Then, 25 or 100 µl of the ringing solution was homogeneously spread over non-selective plate counting agar (PCA) and incubated for 48 h at 37° C. This step was performed by duplicate for each sample. After incubation period, the colony forming units (CFU) were counted and the CFU/g of sample was calculated according to Equation 1 (Eq. 1). Finally, results were transformed to a logarithmic scale (log scale), so to calculate the plasma treatment reduction of microflora rate by comparing each sample with its reference (Eq. 2).

$$\frac{CFU}{g} = \frac{\text{Number of colonies} \times \text{volumen of homogenate (ml)} \times DF}{\text{Volume plated (ml)} \times \text{sample weight (g)}} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

$$\text{Log Reduction} = A B \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

Where: A is the number of viable microorganisms before treatment, and B the number of viable microorganisms after treatment.

3. Results: Optimization of DMSO pre-treatment

3.1. Fibres and plastics cleaning by DMSO from recycled fibers

The source of synthetic fibres and fabrics is the fossil fuel crude oil. It is estimated that 65% of all fibres used in the fashion industry are made from a synthetic material – mainly polyester, but also nylon, acrylic, polypropylene and elastane. Around 98% of all future fibre growth is expected to be in synthetic fibres, 95% of which is expected to be polyester.

As reported in D3.2, the main synthetic fibers used for non-wovens production is polyester. Therefore, dissolution tests in DMSO using recycled polyester fibers (**Fig. 1**) have been conducted to prove the cleaning effect by solvolysis. The bath ratio 1:3 and temperature of 130°C for 2 h treatment time have been optimised by considering both technical (recovery yield up to 95%).

Figure 1. Polyester fibers as gel form after dissolution in DMSO.

Virgin polyester fibers and treated ones have been investigated by IR spectroscopy (**Fig. 2**).

Figure 2. IR spectra of polyester fibers before and after the dissolution in DMSO.

Typical peaks of polyesters are more evident for the fibers treated with DMSO indicating the effectiveness of cleaning process. The obtained gel can be used in conventional spinning processes to obtain new fibers (i.e. gel spinning) for further textile applications in automotive, furniture or clothing sector. The fibers obtained with gel spinning process have usually a higher tensile strength.

3.2. Fibres and plastics cleaning by DMSO from homogeneous ECOBULK project materials

Wind Turbine Blades scraps

Two samples of wind turbine blades scraps were received at NTT facility from CONENOR (Fig. 3):

Figure 3. Samples of wind turbine blades scraps; (A) KORSNÄS from Finland and free from contaminants (origin known and traceable); (B) DEMACQ from Holland (supplied via Virol) and highly contaminated (origin unknown).

Two samples have been initially characterized by IR spectroscopy to show the difference in material composition. Different peaks in the regions 1000 cm^{-1} and $3000\text{-}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. IR spectra of wind turbine blades samples (A) KORSNÄS and (B) DEMACQ.

First tests have been performed to optimize the cleaning process by (**Fig. 5**): bath ratio (1:2-1:5), treatment time and temperature ($100\text{-}200^\circ\text{C}$). After the treatment the insoluble fraction was recovered by filtration and the liquid phase analysed for further investigation by IR spectroscopy. Materials weight reduction have been observed at $T > 100^\circ\text{C} \approx 20\%$ and $T < 100^\circ\text{C} \approx 10\%$ with bath ratio 1:3.

Figure 5. Experimental set-up of wind turbine blades scraps treatment with DMSO.

Figure 6. IR spectra of different treatment temperature for wind turbine blades (WTB) scraps.

A weight reduction has been proved for the post-treatment material in the range 10-20%. Preliminary analysis confirms the solubility of polyurethane (PU) in DMSO at 180°C. The component precipitate as solid particles once the solvent is cooling down and can be recovered by filtration. In order to verify the polyurethane removal from wind turbine blades scraps, neat PU was dissolved in DMSO and the IR spectra compared with liquid fraction obtained by the treatment of wind turbine blades (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. IR spectra of different PU fractions from wind turbine blades (WTB) scraps compared with neat PU fraction.

Table 1 gives the assignments for some of the observed infrared peaks typical of polyurethane components.

Table 1. Assignment of IR major peaks.

Peak Location (cm ⁻¹)	Chemical Structure	Motion
3420-3200	N-H	Stretching
3000-2800	CH ₂ and CH ₃	Stretching
2260	NCO	Stretching
1740	C=O	Non-bonded urethane stretching
1690	C=O	Associated urethane and isocyanurate ring stretch
1510	H-N-C=O Amide II	Combined motion

NTT has also tested another solvent as Sulfolane that is a highly stable and attractive alternative to other more common dipolar aprotic solvents such as DMSO, DMF, DMAC, and NMP. Preliminary tests have shown not significant results respect to the use of DMSO. Furthermore, temperature is one of the most important parameters impacting sulfolane corrosivity. Decomposition of sulfolane with releasing of SO₂ and subsequent formation of H₂SO₃ accelerates at temperatures above 180-200°C, which could lead to higher corrosivity. Therefore, according to these results and its potential for equipment corrosion and subsequent spills for industrial applications, NTT decided not to continue with the experimentation.

CONENOR is interested on the removal of polyurethane contamination in this raw material due to smoke formation during the agglomeration process. The general goal is to have a safe and healthy process for workers and improve the material processability.

According to these results, a pilot system of the tested technology could be set up with CONENOR. In the next period, NTT will discuss with CONENOR the feasibility and requirements for the pilot (e.g. quantities, time schedule, logistics, etc.).

Light fraction from vehicles shredding

ASR is generated from ELVs after shredding and sorting valuable ferrous and non-ferrous metals. It is mainly made up of polymers, metals, rubber, glass, textiles, dirt, etc. The high complexity explains why the development of technologies for recycling ASR is very complicated. One significant reason that made ASR difficult to recycle is its complex composition. As the majority fractions of ASR, plastics greatly contribute to the high complexity. Currently more than 20 kinds of different plastics have been reported

detected in typical ASR mixture which includes polypropylene, polyurethane, polyethylene, polyvinylchloride as main constituents along with other minor fractions.

Therefore, DMSO cleaning of light fraction was investigated for shredding vehicles scraps received from Bellver GBP Metal Group. The fraction is, basically, a mixture of plastics, fabrics, and other minor materials. The best experimental conditions is reported the scheme below (bath ratio 1:3) (**Fig. 8**).

Figure 8. Best experimental conditions for ASR (bath ratio 1:3)

Table 2 reports the experimental conditions used to treat the automotive scraps with DMSO for 2 h. An average weight reduction of about 20% was shown after the treatment at 70°C.

Table 2. Experimental conditions for automotive scraps treatment with DMSO. Weight *i* (initial) and weight *f* (final) are reported for each treatment condition.

Temperature (°C)	Weight <i>i</i> (g)	Weight <i>f</i> (g)	Variation (%)
70	1.44	1.14	-20.83
90	1.58	1.28	-18.98
110	1.54	1.29	-16.23

IR spectra of treated sample was recorded for the material characterization before and after the DMSO treatment. In **Figure 9**, it is obviously indicated that polypropylene, polyethylene, and polyurethane were found from ASR along with some other plastic fractions. There are some obvious absorption peaks that the interest was focused on: 2929 cm^{-1} , 2862 cm^{-1} , 1452 cm^{-1} , 1375 cm^{-1} and 723 cm^{-1} . The absorbance at around 2929 and 2970 cm^{-1} are respectively due to the anti-symmetric deformation of CH₂ group and anti-symmetrical stretching of isopropyl functional group (CH₃) in polypropylene, while the peak at 2862 cm^{-1} is assigned to the CH stretching modes. The two bands at 1452 cm^{-1} and 1375 cm^{-1} are respectively attributed to the anti-symmetrical and symmetrical deformations of CH₃ in polypropylene. The IR band at

about 1473 cm^{-1} was specific for the symmetric deformation of CH_2 in polyethylene. The absorption band at 723 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $-\text{CH}_2$ rocking vibration in polyethylene. The presence of $-\text{NH}$ at 3296 cm^{-1} and CN-H at 1538 cm^{-1} reflect the amide functional groups in polyurethane.

Figure 9. IR spectra of automotive scraps (AS) before and after DMSO treatment at 70°C .

Car scraps

Plastic fraction provided by Tomra comes from cars and its main components are rubber, ABS and PP, that is the mostly used plastic in cars (Fig. 10). The experiments set up are reported in Figure 11.

Figure 10. Plastic fractions from car scraps.

Figure 11. Experimental set-up of car scraps treatment with DMSO.

Solid sample liquefaction was observed for sample ABS/PC (see DSC analysis in **Figure 12** with typical Tg values of ABS and PC polymers). The use of reference band by IR spectroscopy, to compose a relative band, improves accuracy of the methodology for material identification. The absorption at 2233 cm^{-1} was chosen as the analytical band to determine the ABS content. It can be seen that the increase in the intensity of the band at 2237 cm^{-1} is related to the increase in the ABS content. The band 1738 cm^{-1} was chosen as analytical band for PC content in the blend. IR spectra of pure ABS/PC plastic fraction (**Fig. 13**) shown the decrease of analytical band of PC fraction and the increase of peak at 2233 cm^{-1} and other typical bands of ABS after the DMSO treatment (i.e 698 , 764 , 1055 and 1437 cm^{-1}). Therefore, the thermal treatment at 160°C shown a partial removal of PC from ABS/PC blend.

Figure 12. DSC analysis of ABS/PC sample.

Figure 13. IR spectra of white ABS/PC scraps before and after DMSO treatment at 160°C.

Technology Demonstration

The main streams coming from the Physical and Mechanical separation process will be then fed into the solvolysis pilot plant available at NTT (volume of 50 L; see **Figure 14**). Mixture of different polymeric materials can be separated by dissolving each component in dimethylsulfoxide heating the solution at different temperature in the range 160-200°C and different bath ratio in the range 1 kg plastic per 3-5 kg of solvent and treatment time (15-25 minutes). The range has been selected according to preliminary tests carried out at NTT with mixtures of polymers coming from textile industry (polyester fibers) and homogeneous Ecobulk materials (wind turbine blades scraps and ABS/PC components from automotive). Each polymer was selectively separated from the mixture, according to their different softening and melting temperature and recovered by precipitation. Equipment modifications are still in progress and are related to installation of recirculating pumps for the solvent recycling upgrade.

Figure 14. DMSO treatment plant.

The selection of optimum solvents and solvent pairs for extraction is crucial, as well as the reduction of extraction time and solvent usage. However, some organic solvents are hazardous, which limits their usage. Consequently, choosing low-poisonous and cheaper extractors (e.g., natural solvents, such as terpene oils) is one of the future directions for recycling polymers. “Green” solvents are a good choice, for example, SCFs and natural solvents gain a growing interest at present. Therefore, an efficient separation of the polymers would powerfully impulse the recycling industry. Another important thing is an efficient and economic recovery system to recycle the solvents involved in the process of recycling. In the future, the recovery of waste plastics will certainly soar, considering the fact that the diversity of contaminants and materials in plastics continuously shrinks.

The relevant results for DMSO treatment to be added for further recycling and manufacturing/remanufacturing processes in WP4 are the following: 1) the main synthetic fiber used for non-wovens production is polyester and through the dissolution phase we could obtain clean materials in gel form to be re-used with gel spinning process for fibers remanufacturing (to be fed in airlaid technology at Technoplants site); 2) easy

removal of polyurethanes from wind turbine blades preventing smoke formation before the agglomeration process set by Conenor improving the safety of workers.

4. Results: surface activation for reuse by DBD plasma

A section of furniture, automotive and building samples (4 cm x 4 cm) or 100 mg of PS fibers were exposed to DBD plasma treatments using an automatic laboratory plasma system (Lab Plasma System, IRIS. Spain) equipped with two aluminum plate electrodes, both covered by polypropylene dielectrics of 27 x 36 cm and 3 cm of thickness. The equipment is connected to a high voltage alternating current power source (6CP100/50-7,5, Phenix Technologies, Inc., MD), and the applied voltage to the electrode was controlled from a set-up transformer.

4.1. DBD Plasma optimization on material surfaces

Initially, the optimization of DBD-plasma conditions (voltage, gap, contact time, gas, etc) for materials was performed in wood composites and PP blends. A screening of the following plasma conditions was performed:

- ✓ Voltage: 55-65 kV
- ✓ Process time: 30-180 s
- ✓ Gap: 2 cm
- ✓ Gas: Air (75 % HR)

In parallel, a set of untreated samples was kept as control reference to compare the effects of plasma processing.

Secondly, immediately after applying the plasma treatment, the water contact angle (WCA) of untreated and plasma-treated samples was measured. This parameter can be directly related to the wettability or hydrophilic behaviour of the surfaces. In addition, when corresponded, in order to assess the durability of the modified surfaces, the WCA of samples was measured every day during 7 days of storage, at controlled relative humidity (40 %) and temperature (20 °C). All results are reported as average values of contact angles and standard error.

Lastly (*Section 4.2 and 4.3*), once the process time conditions for the plasma treatment had been selected, based on the maximum increasement of the wettability achieved for each material, other set of samples was treated at these optimized conditions to then

evaluate the process efficacy in reducing the initial microflora or the sterilizing effect after inoculation with *S. aureus* (Gram positive) and *E. coli* (Gram negative).

4.1.1 DBD Plasma optimization on furniture

The hydrophilicity of woody products leads to deformation and cracks, which greatly limits its applications (Chen et al., 2017). However, the wood composites received from KEAS were hard and non-porous surfaces. The WCA of the wood composites treated at different time intervals and at different voltage is reported in **Table 3**. An Anova with 2-Factor with replication was performed in Excel, and a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) resulted between different time of plasma treatment, being lower for the group of 180 sec, which showed a good wettability ($WCA < 60$). A non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$) resulted within different voltage treatment, however; when taking into account the time of processing for the voltage 'groups, there was a significant different ($p < 0.05$) between treatments (55 and 65 kV). In any case, time of exposure appeared to be the most important factor in determining the best conditions for the treatment. In fact, a good wettability ($^{\circ} < 60$) resulted when 180 sec were employed for the duration of the treatment (**Table 3**).

Table 3. Water Contact Angle (WCA) of wood composites (furniture from KEAS) treated at different time intervals (30, 60 and 180 sec) at different voltage (55 and 65 kV) with a 2 cm gap

Voltage (kV)	WCA ($^{\circ}$)			Wettability increase (%)		
	30 sec	60 sec	180 sec	30 sec	60 sec	180 sec
55	87.3 \pm 2.9	64.1 \pm 3.1	48.4 \pm 4.1	24.1	44.3	58.0
65	82.0 \pm 8.0	65.2 \pm 1.8	55.0 \pm 3.2	28.8	43.3	52.3

*Results presented as the mean of $n=10$ $r=3$ assays, of each treated formulation.

For that reason, the durability of the modified wood composites was evaluated after a plasma treatment at different voltage (55 and 65 kV) with a 2 cm gap for 180 sec. An Anova Single Factor with replication within wettability increase (%) means was performed in Excel, and a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) resulted between different days after the plasma treatment exposure. A t-Test (paired 2-sample for means) was performed between days compared to day 0, and a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in

wettability of the wood surfaces was observed after 6 days (Fig. 15). In that sense, wood surfaces treated by cold plasma would ideally be reused after 2 days.

*Day 6 and 7 showed significant results ($p < 0.05$). Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ $r=3$ assays, of each treated formulation.

Figure 15. Effect of storage on wettability increase (%) of wood composites (furniture from KEAS) treated at different time intervals (30, 60 and 180 sec) at different voltage (55 and 65 kV) with a 2 cm gap during 180 sec.

Various studies have investigated the surface wettability of wood from several species treated through reduced-pressure plasmas and, more recently, atmospheric DBD plasmas (Acda et al., 2012; Blanchet and Landry, 2015). Some of these studies claimed significant improvements in adhesion strength, but only limited explanations were provided on the role of the active species of the plasma on the wood.

The antimicrobial potential of the plasma treatment was evaluated by counting the initial microbial population of the wood composite and after the treatment at 55 kV during 180 sec with a 2 cm gap (in triplicate). The initial total plate count (mesophilic aerobic population) was 3.7 Log, and the Log reduction was 2.7.

4.1.2 DBD Plasma optimization on automotive

If the oxygen plasma treatment time is too long the plastic will be oxidized. The surface is then not only activated but also etched (Dorai and Kushner, 2003). In this optimization procedure for the plasma treatment, a fixed variable for the voltage was chosen, since

a non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$) resulted within different voltage on wood surfaces. In this sense, the goal of the results from automotive samples was to optimize the time of the treatment.

The WCA of automotive PP blends from MAIER treated at different time intervals and at 55 kV on day 0 showed a good wettability ($^\circ < 60$) (**Table 4**), however; the storage effect reduced the adhesion of the water to the substrate showing a medium wettability (WCA = 60-90) for all treatments (data not shown).

Table 4. Water Contact Angle (WCA) of automotive PP blends (from MAIER) treated at different time intervals (30, 60 and 180 sec) at the same voltage (55 kV) with a 2 cm gap

Voltage (kV)	WCA ($^\circ$)			Wettability increase (%)		
	30 sec	60 sec	180 sec	30 sec	60 sec	180 sec
55	61.4 \pm 2.5	59.9 \pm 1.7	56.3 \pm 1.4	33.5 \pm 3.4	35.1 \pm 2.3	38.9 \pm 1.8

*Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ $r=3$ assays, of each treated formulation.

The wettability increment (%) means of the samples between different time plasma treatments showed no significant difference as per the Anova Single Factor with replication in Excel performed (**Table 4**, $p > 0.05$). Then, 30 sec would be enough to successfully treat automotive samples, which could be related with the non-porous material characteristics.

On the other hand, for all time treatments (30, 60 and 180 s), when evaluating the wettability increment (%) means of the samples between different days after the plasma treatment exposure by an Anova Single Factor with replication in Excel, a significant decrease was observed after day 0 (**Fig. 16**, $p < 0.05$).

*Day 0 showed significant results ($p < 0.05$). Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ $r=3$ assays, of each treated formulation.

Figure 16. Effect of storage on wettability increase (%) of automotive PP blends (from MAIER) treated at different time intervals (30, 60 and 180 sec) at the same voltage (55 kV) with a 2 cm gap

Since the 30 sec time treatment was the optimized, a t-Test (paired 2-sample for means) was performed between days 1-7, and non-significant ($p < 0.05$) values for wettability increment (%) was observed (Fig. 16).

In a similar way, the WCA of automotive PLA blends from MAIER treated at different time intervals and at 55 kV on day 0 showed a good wettability ($^\circ < 60$) (Table 5), however; the storage effect reduced the water contact angle showing a medium wettability (WCA = 60-90) for all treatments (data not shown).

Table 5. Water Contact Angle (WCA) of automotive PLA blends (from MAIER) treated at different time intervals (30, 60 and 180 sec) at the same voltage (55 kV) with a 2 cm gap

Voltage (kV)	WCA ($^\circ$)			Wettability increase (%)		
	30 sec	60 sec	180 sec	30 sec	60 sec	180 sec
55	49.7 \pm 2.2	54.7 \pm 0.9	56.8 \pm 4.2	34.8 \pm 3.5	28.4 \pm 1.4	25.6 \pm 6.8

*Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ $r=3$ assays, of each treated formulation.

In agreement with the PP blends, the wettability increment (%) means of the samples between different time plasma treatments for PLA blends showed no significant difference as per the Anova Single Factor with replication in Excel performed (Table 5, $p > 0.05$). Again, 30 sec would be enough to successfully treat automotive samples.

Furthermore, for all time treatments (30, 60 and 180 s), when evaluating the wettability increment (%) means of the samples between different days after the plasma treatment exposure by an Anova Single Factor with replication in Excel, a significant decrease was observed after day 0 (**Fig. 17**, $p < 0.05$).

According to the optimization results for hydrophobicity enhancement characteristics of the present samples, automotive surfaces (PP and PLA blends) treated by cold plasma would ideally be reused right after the treatment, in comparison with wood surfaces which could be reused after 2 days (*Section 4.1.1*).

*Day 0 showed significant results ($p < 0.05$). Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ $r=3$ assays, of each treated formulation.

Figure 17. Effect of storage on wettability increase (%) of automotive PLA blends (from MAIER) treated at different time intervals (30, 60 and 180 sec) at the same voltage (55 kV) with a 2 cm gap

4.1.3 DBD Plasma effect on textiles

To verify the bactericide potential of the plasma treatment on PS Fiber samples (textiles) provided by NTT partner, each sample was treated for 300 seconds, at 55kV, due to higher surface specific area in comparison to the rest of the samples. The obtained results are shown in **Table 6**, where the antimicrobial effect was calculated as Log Reduction rate by comparing the growth of CFU of controls with the CFU grown after plasma treatment. For calculations, the values of CFU/g of sample (according to **Eq. 1**) were transformed into a logarithm scale (**Eq. 2**). All assays were done by duplicate.

*Table 6. Log reduction effect of DBD plasma treatment on PS fiber samples assayed against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* strains.*

Sample	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
PS fiber	6.9 ± 0.6	6.6 ± 0.5

*Results presented as the mean of $n=2$ $r=2$ assays, of each treated and untreated sample's formulation.

The results confirm a sterilizing effect (total reduction of initial microflora) due to the plasma treatment for both strains of microorganisms assayed. The antibacterial effect calculated as Log reduction was in the range of 6.5 to 7, being greater for *S. aureus* (Gram positive). On the other hand, *E. coli* (Gram negative) presented the more resistant behaviour.

4.2.

4.3. Optimized conditions on furniture surfaces

According to *Section 4.1.1*, the cold plasma treatment of surfaces at 55 kV during 180 sec would be enough to successfully treat furniture surfaces.

Board samples from KEAS (produced in laboratory press with % 100 recycled particles) were studied. KEAS woody products showed cracks, which were limited for this application. Since their nature showed high hydrophilicity, KEAS samples were treated with optimized conditions for cold plasma treatment as follows:

- ✓ Voltage: 55 kV
- ✓ Process time: 30 s
- ✓ Gap: 2 cm
- ✓ Gas: Air (75 % HR)

4.2.1. Water Contact Angle (WCA)

To verify the adhesion properties of the optimized plasma treatment conditions for 30 seconds from furniture samples, the sessile technique was calculated according to *Section 2.3*. In this case, picture was taken right away after adding the drop (**Fig. 18**), since absorption of the water drop was observed for these hydrophilic surfaces.

Figure 18. WCA after cold plasma treatment on board furniture panels at 55 kV during 30 sec.

For this sample, the wettability modification rate after the plasma treatment was 21.4 % (n=5 r=3 assays).

4.2.2. Sterilizing effect

The results confirm a sterilizing effect of Log Reduction of 3.8 ± 0.4 for *S. aureus* (total reduction of initial microflora) due to the plasma treatment. On the other hand, *E. coli* (Gram negative) presented <10 CFU/g in both control and treated samples, probably due to the fact that the scrapping method was performed when the water drops were already absorbed to the inner part of the furniture material.

4.3. Optimized conditions on automotive surfaces

In Section 4.1.2, optimized conditions for cold plasma treatment on automotive samples were as follows:

- ✓ Voltage: 55 kV
- ✓ Process time: 30 s
- ✓ Gap: 2 cm
- ✓ Gas: Air (75 % HR)

Those process parameters were chosen to treat 5 automotive samples from MAIER.

4.3.1. Water Contact Angle (WCA)

To verify the adhesion properties of the optimized plasma treatment conditions from automotive samples, the sessile technique was calculated according to *Section 2.3* for samples composed of PP and PLA blends (**Fig. 19**).

*Results presented as the mean of $n=10$ of each treated and untreated sample's formulation.

Figure 19. Effect of cold plasma on water contact angle (WCA, °) on automotive surfaces treated at 55 kV for 30 sec with a 2 cm gap.

In **Figure 20**, the wettability increase (%) is presented for automotive samples, based on results from **Fig. 19**. The sample PLA 2.2 showed the best wettability characteristics of automotive samples, which is in line with the WCA results of the PLA 2.1 sample compared to PP blends in *Section 4.1.2*. In fact, PLA is a more hydrophobic substance in comparison to PP.

Figure 20. Wettability increase (%) of automotive samples treated at 55 kV for 30 sec with a 2 cm gap.

4.3.2. Sterilizing effect

To verify the bactericide potential of the optimized plasma treatment conditions from automotive samples, the antimicrobial effect was calculated according to *Section 2.4* for a sample composed of PLA and PP blends. All assays were done in duplicate. In **Table 7**, the results confirm a sterilizing effect due to the plasma treatment for both strains of microorganisms assayed. The antibacterial effect calculated as Log reduction was in the range of 3 to 4, by achieving a total inactivation of both inoculum (*E. Coli* and *S. Aureus*).

Table 7. Log reduction effect of DBD plasma treatment on a building sample based of PLA blends assayed against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* strains.

Sample	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
PLA 2.1	3.1 ± 0.1	3.9 ± 0.4
PPNF 1.1	3.0 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.0

*Results presented as the mean of $n=2$ $r=2$ assay, of each treated and untreated sample's formulation.

Along with microbiology results from *Section 4.1.3.* and *4.2.2*, the above results are in line with other literature which concludes that cold plasma can be very effective against cells and spores on surfaces with more than 4 log reductions (Hati *et al.*, 2012).

4.4. Optimized conditions on building surfaces

In construction and building, plasma treatment of polymeric fibers has demonstrated to be effective in improving the flexural performance and toughness of fiber reinforced concrete composites (Zhang, Gopalaratnam and Yasuda, 2000). To verify the optimized conditions of plasma treatment on building recycled polymeric materials samples (**Fig. 21**), provided by CONENOR partner, each sample was treated for 30 seconds at 55kV. The bactericide potential of the materials and the adhesion characteristics enhancement of the plasma processing was studied.

Figure 21. Building samples (recycled polymeric materials); 1= CON.1, 2= CON.2, 3= CON.3, and 4= CON.4.

4.4.1. Water Contact Angle (WCA)

To verify the adhesion properties of the optimized plasma treatment conditions from building samples, the sessile technique was calculated according to *Section 2.3*. In **Figure 22**, the values of WCA ($n=5$, $r=1$) before and after plasma treatment are shown on samples CON.1, CON.2, CON.3, and CON.4.

*Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ of each treated and untreated sample's formulation.

Figure 22. WCA of building samples (recycled polymeric materials)

All samples decreased its WCA after the plasma treatment (**Fig. 22**), and the wettability modification rate (%) of each treated sample (**Table 8**) appeared to be higher for sample CON.2 (49.5 %) and CON.4 (35 %).

Table 8. Wettability increase (%) of building samples (recycled polymeric materials)

Sample	Wettability increase (%)
CON.1	26.3
CON.2	49.5
CON.3	11.6
CON.4	35.0

* Results presented as the mean of $n=5$ $r=1$ assay, of each treated formulation.

4.4.2. Sterilizing effect

The obtained results are shown in **Table 9**, where the antimicrobial effect was calculated according to *Section 2.4*. All assays were done once, because no duplicates were received for these samples.

Table 9. Log reduction effect of DBD plasma treatment on polymeric materials samples (building) samples assayed against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* strains.

Sample	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
CON.1	4.2	3.2
CON.2	0.0	3.5
CON.3	0.0	3.5
CON.4	1.8	3.5

*Results presented as the mean of $n=2$ $r=1$ assay, of each treated and untreated sample's formulation.

The results confirm a sterilizing effect due to the plasma treatment for both strains of microorganisms assayed. The antibacterial effect calculated as Log reduction was in the range of 2 to 4, being greater for *E. Coli* (Gram positive). On the other hand, *S. Aureus* (Gram negative) presented the more resistant behaviour.

5. Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable has covered the material conditioning pre-treatments, along with a methodology to study the chemical separation with Dimethylsulphoxide and the Cold plasma processing. Results of the assayed samples of pre-treated materials (Task 3.4.) will be useful to Ecobulk project partners who are in charge of doing the extrusion of pellets, since this information will allow them to validate the use of materials obtained with and without plasma pre-treatment, as well as with other chemical compatibilizers.

Moreover, results from Task 5.3.3 in relation with quality assessments of recycled materials will be taken into consideration for deciding whether to apply the plasma treatment (Task 3.4) or not.

DMSO process has proved the effectiveness in fibers and plastic cleaning for further application of raw materials in industrial processes involved in the project. In case of polyesters fibers, one of the thermoplastic fibers used in non-wovens production (Task 3.2), contaminants were removed obtaining the material gelification that can be re-manufactured in new fibers again by spinning process and further re-use in airlaid technology by Technoplants. Polyurethane particles were removed from wind turbine blades scraps obtaining a raw material safer for agglomeration process tested by Conenor. The recovered PU can be used to produce parts of car's interior that are all made with polyurethane foams. Further investigations for industrial process validation should be performed to evaluate the environmental and economical sustainability. Considering the cost of industrial DMSO of about 1 €/kg, the process cost could be estimated about 2 €/kg. Pilot scale implementation should be discussed with industrial partners like Conenor according to the contamination degree of wind turbine blades scraps provided by other external companies involved in material size reduction.

Plasma treatment have been successfully applied for surface modification of automotive and building materials in the present deliverable, in order to meet protection for the materials and preparation for other process: dyeing, varnishing, gluing, antifriction treatment, etc. The proposed process parameters for automotive surfaces (55 kV during 180 sec, 2 cm gap at atmospheric pressure) and obtained results could be useful to the consortium (MAIER) and to the public in general in the following sectors for decontamination: plastic and rubber industry, medical plastics, automotive components and aerospace components, among others.

The proposed process parameters for furniture (55 kV during 180 sec, 2 cm gap at atmospheric pressure) and obtained results could be useful to the consortium (KEAS) and to the public in general in furniture, since durability/resistance of furniture surfaces can be improved by microbial decontamination and substantially better adhesion with the coating. The WCA (°) achieved at those parameters was 48.4 ± 4.1 and the initial total plate count was reduced by 2.7 Log.

In the scale-up to pilot-scale and commercial-scale processing, batch systems face technical hurdles related to the speed and volume of throughput and cannot be predicted with certainty. Ongoing costs based on consumables, however, can be predicted with some degree of confidence. This is because all cold plasma systems, of whatever design, must use electricity and a feed gas of some kind. Assuming a scale factor of two orders of magnitude in going from lab scale to commercial scale, power consumption of plasma may be as much as 90 kW, comparable to other types of large-scale industrial equipment. Assuming \$0.05 per kWh, electricity cost per 1,000 hours of

operation would be approximately \$4,500. In regards the type of gas, cold plasma systems that use helium will be significantly more expensive to operate at a commercial scale than cold plasma systems that use air (0 \$), as per this deliverable, or other mixtures of nitrogen and oxygen.

As per the results in the present deliverable, the antimicrobial and hydrophilicity mode of action of cold plasma treatment at lab-scale has been successfully optimized in three different sectors (automotive, building and furniture). In this sense, no further trials/tests are planned with WP3 partners beyond lab-scale (e.g. Conenor, KEAS, Netcomposites, Tecnar, etc.), since the next step would be to study the economic feasibility of scaling-up, that seems to be not aligned with the current commercial intention of the Partners involved (e.g KEAS).

As final conclusion DBD plasma was demonstrated to be a useful technology for improving both the wettability of the materials under studies (that implies an increased compatibility of the materials with the applied coatings) and the decontamination effect of the technology. The companies involved are not yet ready for its implementation at pilot level due to specific technical issues (materials dimensions) and to a misalignment of the current commercial strategy of the companies, but this work provides them a solid proof of concept that the proposed technology could be applied as cheap solution for increasing the kinetics of impregnation of the in-line application of coatings as well as for the decontamination of materials that will be dedicated to specific functions (e.g automotive internal components).

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